

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EVALUATING THE ADAPTATION OF SEVERAL SOYBEAN VARIETIES ON GRAY SOIL AMENDED WITH BIOCHAR IN NORTHERN VIETNAM

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the adaptation of several soybean (*Glycine max* L.) varieties grown on gray soil amended with biochar in Northern Vietnam. Gray soil, characterized by low fertility and poor structure, poses significant challenges for sustainable agriculture. Biochar, a carbon-rich product derived from organic biomass, has been recognized for its potential to improve soil properties and enhance crop productivity. Field experiments were conducted with different soybean varieties to assess their growth performance, yield, and physiological responses to biochar amendments. Data collected on plant height, leaf area, chlorophyll content, nodulation, and yield components were analyzed to determine the effectiveness of biochar in improving soybean growth under these soil conditions. The results indicated that biochar amendment significantly enhanced soil properties, leading to improved plant growth and yield in most soybean varieties tested. This research provides valuable insights into the potential benefits of biochar for soybean cultivation on gray soils in Northern Vietnam, contributing to the development of sustainable agricultural practices in the region.

Keywords: Soybean varieties, Gray soil, Biochar amendment, Northern Vietnam, Adaptation evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) is a globally significant legume, valued for its high protein and oil content, and plays a crucial role in human nutrition, animal feed, and various industrial applications. In Vietnam, soybean cultivation is vital for both economic and food security purposes. However, the productivity of soybean is often constrained by soil conditions, particularly in regions with gray soils. Gray soils, prevalent in Northern Vietnam, are characterized by low organic matter content, poor structure, and limited nutrient availability, which adversely affect crop growth and yield.

Biochar, a stable carbon-rich product obtained from the pyrolysis of organic biomass, has gained attention for its potential to improve soil health and enhance agricultural productivity. Biochar amendments have been reported to improve soil properties, including increased water retention, enhanced nutrient availability, and improved soil microbial activity. These

benefits suggest that biochar could be a viable amendment to mitigate the limitations of gray soils and support sustainable soybean production.

This study aims to evaluate the adaptation and performance of several soybean varieties grown on gray soil amended with biochar in Northern Vietnam. By examining plant growth, physiological responses, and yield characteristics, this research seeks to identify the most suitable soybean varieties for cultivation under these amended soil conditions. The findings will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of biochar as a soil amendment and its potential to improve soybean productivity in regions with challenging soil conditions. This research contributes to the broader goal of developing sustainable agricultural practices that enhance crop production while maintaining soil health in Northern Vietnam.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material: The soybean varieties participating in the experiment have their origins in Table 1

Table 1:

Origin of the experimental soybean varieties	
Symbol	Origin and provenance
DT84 (Control)	The Vietnam Institute of Agricultural Genetics selected and bred from the hybrid combination DT80 × DH4 induced mutation.
DT33	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected from the hybrid combination between two pure lines, 20.06 × 12.1
DT32	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected a line from the combination (10.34 (mother) / 10.51 (father)).
DT11	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected and bred from the hybrid combination M103 × DT2000 using sexual hybridization combined with molecular markers to select genotypes resistant to rust disease.
D9	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops hybridized and selected using sexual hybridization combined with molecular markers to select genotypes resistant to rust disease from the hybrid combination TL7 × DT2000.
DT22	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected and bred from a mutant line of the hybrid seeds (DT95 × DT12).
DT35	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected and bred from hybrid lines of the combination (DT26/D08.12).
DT51	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected from the hybrid combination between LS17 × DT2001.
D2101	The Vietnam Institute of Food Crops selected and bred using sexual hybridization from the hybrid combination D95 × D9037.

Method:

The experiment comprised 9 soybean varieties, arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 3 replications. Experimental plot area: 10 m² (2 m × 5 m); density: 30 plants/m². Fertilization rate per hectare: 30 kg N + 90 kg P₂O₅ + 60 kg K₂O + 2 tons of

biochar. The biochar, derived from rice straw and corn stalks, was pyrolyzed at 500°C for 3 hours. The nutrient content of the biochar used in the experiment is presented in Table 2.

Table 2:

content in biochar							
Parameter	pH _{KCl}	Carbon total (%)	Nitrogen total (%)	P ₂ O ₅ total (%)	K ₂ O total (%)	CaO total (%)	MgO total (%)
Value	6,12	44,12	0,62	0,32	0,64	0,21	0,11

The technical measures and monitoring criteria were applied according to the Vietnamese National Technical Regulation on the testing of agronomic and utilization value of soybean varieties (QCVN 01-58:2011/BNNPTNT).

- Data were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with IRRISTAT 5.0 software and Excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3.

Growth stages of soybean varieties				
Varieties	Germination rate (%)	Time from Germination to Flowering (days)	Time from Flowering to Harvest (days)	Growth duration (days)
DT84	92,3	32	67	95
DT33	92,1	33	62	95
DT32	92,7	35	65	98
DT11	94,2	36	60	96
D9	95,2	33	63	97
DT22	93,0	34	66	101
DT35	91,6	35	63	94
DT51	92,3	36	64	95
D2101	93,2	34	63	96

The experimental results presented in Table 3 indicate that the soybean varieties exhibit high germination rates, ranging from 91.6% to 95.2%. The time from germination to flowering for these soybean varieties

ranges from 32 to 36 days. Among them, the varieties DT11 and DT51 have the longest time to flowering, which is 36 days. The time from flowering to harvest varies between 60 and 67 days, reflecting differences in

maturation times among the varieties. The total growth duration for the soybean varieties ranges from 94 to 101 days. Specifically, the variety DT35 has the shortest

growth duration of 94 days, while the variety DT22 has the longest growth duration, extending up to 101 days.

Table 4.

Some growth parameters of soybean varieties

Varieties	Final plant height (cm)	Pod insertion height (cm)	Number of primary branches (branches)	Number of effective internodes (internodes)
DT84	48,20	7,21	1,93	9,83
DT33	51,31	7,69	1,97	9,23
DT32	54,43	7,91	1,87	10,54
DT11	53,26	7,73	2,07	10,30
D9	49,26	7,66	2,03	9,63
DT22	52,24	8,40	2,33	10,10
DT35	53,62	7,97	2,54	10,55
DT51	49,36	7,67	2,43	9,80
D2101	49,89	7,10	1,88	9,98
CV (%)	4,2	4,27	3,89	4,3
LSD _{0,05}	1,18	0,52	0,15	0,66

The evaluation results of growth and development characteristics of the soybean varieties, as presented in Table 4, show that the plant height of the varieties ranges from 48.20 to 54.43 cm. Among these, the DT32 variety has the tallest plant height at 54.43 cm, while the DT84 variety has the shortest plant height at 48.20 cm.

Pod insertion height is a crucial parameter in soybean breeding, especially for mechanized harvesting. A low pod insertion height may result in harvesting machines failing to collect all the produce, leading to loss and reduced yield. Conversely, an excessively high pod insertion height may limit the potential yield of the variety. Therefore, pod insertion height is inversely correlated with crop yield. According to the study, a pod insertion height ≥ 10 cm is suitable for current soybean

harvesting machines. The results show that the pod insertion height of the tested varieties ranges from 7.10 to 8.40 cm. Notably, the D2101 variety has a pod insertion height of 8.40 cm, which is significantly lower than the control variety (7.21 cm) with a 95% statistical significance; whereas other varieties have a higher pod insertion height compared to the control.

The number of primary branches ranges from 1.88 to 2.54 branches, with the DT35 variety having the highest number and the DT32 variety having the lowest. The number of effective internodes varies from 9.23 to 10.55 internodes. The DT32, DT11, DT22, DT35, and D2101 varieties have significantly more effective internodes compared to the control variety, with a 95% statistical significance.

Table 5.

Some yield-contributing factors of the experimental soybean varieties

Varieties	Total number of pods per plant (pods)	Pod setting rate (%)	Single-seed pod ratio (%)	Two-seed pod ratio (%)	Three-seed pod ratio (%)	Thousand-seed weight (grams)
DT84	32,10	95,40	12,63	63,84	23,53	170,29
DT33	29,10	96,55	11,27	57,13	31,6	175,22
DT32	32,12	94,00	9,96	59,39	30,65	168,41
DT11	33,54	93,32	9,30	62,32	28,38	165,23
D9	33,15	94,15	9,24	62,35	28,41	167,38
DT22	34,33	95,21	9,64	65,85	24,51	170,35
DT35	32,33	95,20	7,51	64,87	27,62	166,26
DT51	34,12	96,21	10,73	56,56	32,71	163,54
D2101	34,27	94,19	9,35	51,44	39,21	168,14
CV (%)	5,2	5,12	5,6	4,14	6,1	2,95
LSD _{0,05}	1,47	2,33	0,94	1,81	2,25	12,12

The evaluation of yield components for the tested soybean varieties, as presented in Table 5, reveals that the total number of pods per plant ranges from 29.10 to 34.27. The seed filling rate varies between 93.32% and 96.21%, with the control variety DT84 exhibiting a

seed filling rate of 95.4%. All other varieties differ significantly from the control in terms of seed filling rate at a 95% confidence level.

The proportion of two-seeded pods is significantly lower for all varieties compared to the control at a 95% probability level, whereas the proportion of three-

seeded pods is significantly higher than that of the control, with a 95% confidence level.

The 1000-seed weight of the soybean varieties ranges from 163.54 to 170.35 grams, with no significant differences observed compared to the control at a 95% confidence level.

Table 6.

Correlation coefficients between growth stages and individual yield of soybean varieties

Flowering time	Seed maturity duration	Growth duration	Individual yield
Flowering time	1		
Seed maturity duration	-0,53	1	
Growth duration	-0,26	0,96	1
Individual yield	0,68	-0,89	-0,77

In this study, the period from the onset of flowering to pod maturation is longer than the period from planting to the onset of flowering. There is a significant positive correlation between the duration from flowering to pod maturation and the total growth period, with a correlation coefficient of 0.96 (Table 6). Conversely, the correlation coefficient between the time from sowing to flowering and the total growth period is -0.26. These correlation values suggest that the total growth period is inversely related to the time from planting to

flowering but positively related to the time from flowering to pod maturation. Additionally, the correlations between individual yield and the time from germination to flowering, from flowering to pod maturation, and the total growth period are 0.68, -0.89, and -0.77, respectively. This indicates that individual yield is positively correlated with the time from germination to flowering but negatively correlated with both the time from flowering to pod maturation and the total growth period.

Table 7.

Actual yield of experimental soybean lines and varieties

Varieties	Individual yield (grams/plant)	Theoretical yield (tons/ha)	Actual yield (tons/ha)
DT84	7,81	2,32	1,53
DT33	9,65	2,85	1,63
DT32	9,16	2,75	1,62
DT11	10,28	2,83	1,78
D9	8,91	2,69	1,73
DT22	9,06	2,71	1,62
DT35	9,92	2,88	1,66
DT51	7,92	2,48	1,64
D2101	8,97	2,69	1,62
CV (%)	4,10	3,13	4,20
LSD _{0,05}	0,63	0,25	0,06

Yield is a crucial criterion for evaluating the performance of experimental soybean varieties. The results presented in Table 7 indicate that the individual yield of the varieties ranged from 7.81 to 10.28 g/plant, with the DT11 variety showing the highest yield and the control variety DT84 showing the lowest. The theoretical yield ranged from 2.32 to 3.13 tons/ha, with all experimental varieties exhibiting higher theoretical yields compared to the control variety, at a 95% confidence level. The actual yield of the varieties ranged from 1.53 to 1.78 tons/ha, with all experimental varieties achieving higher actual yields compared to the DT84 control variety, with this difference being statistically significant at the 95% confidence level.

CONCLUSION

The experimental results reveal several key findings. The soybean varieties exhibit high germination

rates, ranging from 91.6% to 95.2%. The time from germination to flowering varies between 32 to 36 days, with DT11 and DT51 having the longest duration.

The total growth duration spans from 94 to 101 days, with DT35 showing the shortest growth period and DT22 the longest. Plant heights range from 48.20 cm to 54.43 cm, with DT32 being the tallest and DT84 the shortest. Pod insertion heights range from 7.10 cm to 8.40 cm, with D2101 having the highest insertion height, which is favorable for mechanized harvesting.

The number of primary branches per plant ranges from 1.88 to 2.54, with DT35 having the most branches, while the number of effective internodes varies from 9.23 to 10.55, with several varieties having significantly more internodes than the control.

Yield components show that the number of pods per plant ranges from 29.10 to 34.27, and seed filling rates vary between 93.32% and 96.21%, with significant differences compared to the control. The proportion of two-seeded pods is lower, while three-seeded

Pods are more prevalent compared to the control. Individual yields range from 7.81 to 10.28 g/plant, with DT11 achieving the highest yield.

The theoretical yield ranges from 2.32 to 3.13 tons/ha, and actual yields range from 1.53 to 1.78 tons/ha, with all experimental varieties outperforming the control. Correlations indicate that individual yield is positively related to the time from germination to flowering but negatively related to the time from flowering to pod maturation and the total growth period.

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